

Farm machinery

Effect of water depth on field capacity and field efficiency of soil preparation equipment

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We used minitractor, animal, and human power to prepare fields for transplanting in a study of differences in field capacity and field efficiency.

Treatments were no standing water and 5-10 cm and 15-20 cm water depth, in a factorial design with 3 replications.

Experimental plots were 25 × 20 m at Lanrang Experimental Farm in 1983 dry season. Highest average field capacities were as follows: minitractor, 0.156 ha/h; animal power, 0.111 ha/h; and human power, 0.092 ha/h, with respective field efficiencies of 72.7, 79.9, and 63.9% (Table 1, 2). □

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Farming systems

Performance of rice varieties intercropped with pigeonpea

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We studied the performance of three rice varieties intercropped with pigeonpea (Type 21) in a randomized block design with 3 replications in 1987 wet season. Soil was sandy loam, with

Table 1. Effective field capacity of soil preparation equipment at 3 water depths (0, 5-10 cm, 15-20 cm). Lanrang, Sidrap, Indonesia, 1983.

Power source	Land preparation ^a	Effective field capacity ^b (ha/h)		
		0	5-10 cm	15-20 cm
Minitractor	Phase 1	0.067 a	0.136 c	0.084 b
	Phase 2	0.077 a	0.130 b	0.133 b
	Phase 3	0.132 a	0.201 b	0.155 ab
	Mean	0.092 a	0.156 c	0.124 b
Bullock (1 pair)	Phase 1	0.026 a	0.035 a	0.031 a
	Phase 2	0.030 a	0.037 b	0.032 a
	Phase 3	0.150 a	0.260 c	0.210 b
	Mean	0.069 a	0.111 c	0.091 b
Manual labor (5 men)	Phase 1	0.027 a	0.039 b	0.049 b
	Phase 2	0.123 a	0.114 a	0.093 a
	Phase 3	0.116 a	0.123 a	0.093 a
	Mean	0.089 b	0.092 b	0.078 a

^aPhase 1 = rotary plow and mini tractor, plow and bullocks, hoe and manual labor; phase 2 = rotary plow, plow, hoe; phase 3 = rotary plow, harrow, hoe. ^bIn a row, numbers followed by the same letter do not differ significantly at 5% DMRT.

Table 2. Field efficiency of power for land preparation at 3 water depths (0, 5-10 cm, 15-20 cm). Lanrang, Sidrap, Indonesia, 1983.

Power source	Land preparation ^a	Field efficiency (%)		
		0 cm	5-10 cm	15-20 cm
Minitractor	Phase 1	31.3	63.6	39.3
	Phase 2	36.0	60.7	62.1
	Phase 3	61.7	93.9	72.4
	Mean	43.0	72.7	57.9
Bullock (1 pair)	Phase 1	61.9	83.3	73.8
	Phase 2	71.4	88.1	76.2
	Phase 3	39.5	68.4	55.3
	Mean	57.6	79.9	68.4
Manual labor (5 men)	Phase 1	18.8	27.1	34.0
	Phase 2	85.4	79.2	64.6
	Phase 3	80.6	85.4	64.6
	Mean	61.6	63.9	54.4

^aSee footnote^a in Table 1.

Rice and pigeonpea yields in monocrop and intercrop. Uttar Pradesh, India, 1987.

Treatment	Rice yield (t/ha)	Pigeonpea yield (t/ha)	Land equivalent ratio
Single crop Arhar T21		1.86	1.0
Single crop rice NDR84	1.8	—	1.0
Single crop rice NDR118	1.5	—	1.0
Single crop rice Narendra 1	2.0	—	1.0
Rice NDR84 + Arhar T21	1.4	1.27	1.49
Rice NDR118 + Arhar T21	1.3	1.28	1.58
Rice Narendra + Arhar T21	1.7	0.98	1.43
LSD (P=0.05)	0.6	0.40	
CV (%)	13.1	6.69	

pH 7.5 and 0.58% organic matter.

The 170-175 d pigeonpea cultivar and short-duration rice cultivars NDR84,

NDR 118, and Narendra 118 were sown as single crops and intercrops. Spacing (60 cm between rows and 20 cm between